

Academic Guidelines and Recommendations for Integrating Green Coding Aspects into Curricula of Higher Education

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Supplementary Material B – Exemplary Structure of a Stand-Alone Course

Lecture Number	Lesson Type	Content
1	Lecture	The course starts with an introduction, delving into Sustainability Theory and exploring its significance, purpose, and implementation in software development. Green software and sustainable software development are also discussed in detail.
2	Lecture	In this session, we delve into the GREENSOFT Framework, exploring its various dimensions, including the Life Cycle of Software products, Sustainability Criteria and Metrics, Procedure Models, Recommendations, and Tools.
3	Lab (Project)	Project 1 - Introduction to Project 1. This practical session initiates students into measuring software energy consumption of example software written in Java and Python. The importance of energy-efficient programming is also emphasized.
4	Lab (Project)	Project 1 - Measuring software energy consumption. Students receive insightful knowledge regarding the SPELL Method, which is a comprehensive method for analyzing the amount of energy consumed by software applications. The primary areas of focus are the various use cases, performance, preferences, and operational settings, as well as the distinctions between each programming language (Java, Python). In class, they are going to talk about and present the results of the measurements that they took.
5	Lecture	This lecture contrasts the Agile Methods with the Waterfall Model in the context of Sustainability. It does so by analyzing the benefits and drawbacks of each approach when it comes to creating environmentally responsible software.
6	Project	Project 2 - Introduction to Project 2. This project starts by introducing students to the task of defining principles and guidelines for sustainable software development and green coding. It also focuses on the different methods of energy-efficient programming.
7	Project	Project 2 - Group discussion and refining the development of guidelines. Students actively participate in group discussions, collaborating to establish actionable guidelines that prioritize sustainability in software engineering. This process results from a written guidelines list that includes best practices and focus areas.
8	Project	An evaluation survey and summary of Project 1 and Project 2 are conducted. An introduction to Project 3 is also provided, setting the stage for the subsequent project. Students must also evaluate the course's first half and give feedback. This feedback is a valuable resource to reflect upon and extract valuable lessons for continuous improvement.
9	Project	A steering meeting is held to guide and oversee the progress of Project 3.
10	Project	Another steering meeting is conducted to ensure the project remains on track and aligned with sustainability objectives.

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11	Lecture	This lecture explores the vital role of AI in driving sustainability, particularly in environmentally friendly software development. We highlight the significance of future thinking to leverage AI's potential in tackling environmental challenges and creating a sustainable future.
12	Project	A steering meeting is convened to monitor and support the ongoing efforts of Project 3.
13	Project	Another steering meeting takes place to provide continuous guidance and ensure the effective development of Project 3.
14	Project	A final steering meeting is held to oversee the concluding stages of Project 3 and its alignment with sustainability principles.
15	Presentation	This session showcases student demos, where they present their projects and demonstrate how their software aligns with sustainable practices.
16	Presentation	The final round of student demos is conducted, providing a platform to showcase their completed projects and the successful integration of sustainability.
17	Lecture	As the Semester approaches, a critical end-of-semester discussion takes place, creating a collaborative environment for students and educators to reflect on the overall learning experience. This session promotes the open exchange of ideas and constructive feedback to facilitate continuous improvement. Furthermore, this discussion is a foundation for the following year's course, particularly with incoming students. Students play an important role in shaping the new projects through active participation, ensuring a Co-Creation approach. This collaborative effort contributes to the creation of a course that is tailored to the needs and interests of the students.